

Risk Management of Liquidity: Problematic of the Behavior of the Moroccan Commercial Banks Customers

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Abstract

The bank customers' behaviors are seen to be is an essential issue regarding asset liability management banking. In addition, based on the latest the Basel Committee's recommendations, it seems to be considered a tool of a better risk management. The present paper proposes a modeling regarding the bank customers' behaviors where it attempts to see, more specifically, for customer deposits among Moroccan commercial banks. The presented data of this study are presented based on the summary statements (balance sheets) for determining these deposits' portions, stabled in function of time to be used by banks granting loans as well as minimizing the transformation risks and liquidity risks. This study concluded that the depositors businesses have no visible financial behaviors towards their demand deposits based on the presented results. Such kind of conclusion can allow banks not to take into account factors regarding the interest rates of short-terms as impacting the available current accounts' volume.

Introduction

Nowadays, if any organization wants to be successful in the market in which it operates, it must make all efforts to satisfy the needs of its customers. The extent to which it can build and maintain strong relationships with them depends on how it is able to understand the behavior of its customers (Fejza et al., 2018).

In particular, commercial banks are considered as receptacles in which funds accumulate in the form of deposits to be lent again under specific conditions to those who need them, as well as providing various services in a way that contributes to financing the various activities of the national economy. Banks Customers are looking for a safe and reliable party to deposit their money, preserve and use it when needed. They are also looking for a source that enables them to fulfill their obligations and provides them with financial resources that secure their needs. Therefore, trust in the bank is very important, as its success in achieving the goal of survival and growth depends to a large extent on the confidence of the customers in it, which in turn depends on many criteria such as solvency, liquidity and accuracy in the performance of the business (Burkani, 2016).

On the other hand, it is well known that every institution operating in the banking or financial market faces challenges and risks, especially in managing customer satisfaction and inquiries. However, the ultimate goal is to keep enough funds in the treasury in order to be relevant while analyzing the balance sheet, thus winning a high ranking compared to other competitors (Eloitri, 2017). And among these risks that banks face is liquidity risk. It arises when the bank will not be able to meet commitments made as they fall due. So it is a result of the mismatch between the different liquidity flows across the entire bank balance sheet (Regragui and Meriouh, 2015)

Recently, liquidity risk, is considered as the biggest risk worrying the banking sector. Immediately after the 2008 international crisis, Basel updated and developed new standards and rules to support all financial actors and protect their activities from liquidity risks (Eloitri, 2017). Moreover, risk management is very important in the banking sector since the instability of the global economy and the crisis in some euro-zone countries in recent years have clearly demonstrated the interconnectedness of different types of risks in the banking sector. At present, global experience shows that timely analysis and assessment of liquidity risk is a key issue in banking risk management. (Jaksybekova et al., 2018).

This is the case with sight deposits that we have proposed a conventional flow law for. This requires modeling of their concept since their development is dependent on customer behavior, which may be economic, seasonal, or financial. This is done through the application of the deposit evaluation model which will make it possible to establish a stabilization threshold for demand deposits which are part of these deposits that the bank will provide for its various functions and without significant payment risk (Regragui and Meriouh, 2015)

A commercial bank's liquidity represents a potential use of its assets as sources of cash or immediate transfer to cash, and the asset's ability to maintain its permanent face value. Problems related to liquidity

management in commercial banks are an important issue that any bank considers. If force majeure results in the bank's inability to provide liquidity, it may go bankrupt (Jaksybekova et al., 2018). And Morocco is among the countries that include a banking system consisting of commercial banks where this study seeks to address.

Each bank challenges customer satisfaction as well as keeping treasury in a comfortable balance, due to this maturity shift that occurs naturally by shifting short and long term deposits, allowing the bank to have the best rating (Eloitri, 2017). The behavior of bank customers is a major issue of asset liability management banking and is one of the latest recommendations of the Basel Committee with a view to better risk management (Regragui and Meriouh, 2015). Under current economic conditions, organizations see their efficient risk management as an important issue to provide their financial stability (Jaksybekova et al., 2018). Particularly, Liquidity management involves the ability of banks to attract low-cost deposits to maximize brokerage margins for this shift. (Eloitri, 2017). It is considered as one of the topics of interest to researchers due to its great economic importance, ambiguity and questions surrounding it where banking institutions are required to manage their liquidity and employ it in a way that achieves profits for them, which represents the ultimate goal of any business (Berger, Bouwman, Kick, & Schaeck, 2016).

Liquidity in Moroccan banks has moved from a state of excess liquidity to a persistent liquidity deficit since 2007 (Mehdi & Abderrassoul, 2014). Thus, global experience shows that timely analysis and assessment of liquidity risk is a key issue in banking risk management (Jaksybekova et al., 2018). Indeed, sight deposits are a very important source of liquidity risk, they are the largest debt of the bank and which have no contractual flow as is the case for the majority of other balance sheet items. They are therefore not due: these amounts may vary in both directions and without delay. Statistically, however, a significant fraction of sight deposits is stable (Regragui and Meriouh, 2015).

Accordingly, how can we value these sight deposits? In other words, what is the flow model for sight deposits of Moroccan commercial banks? and what is the stable part of these deposits, as a function of time that these banks could use to grant loans while minimizing the risk of liquidity and transformation?

1. Liquidity risk

According to (Regragui and Meriouh, 2015), Liquidity risk translates into the bank's inability to meet its commitments on the date they become due. It arises when unexpected needs are encountered by the bank and it cannot meet them from its liquid assets. While Kostyuchenko believes that it means a risk of loss caused by inappropriate repayment periods of liabilities and assets. This loss could cover the shortfall in profit due to diversion of resources to support liquidity (Kostyuchenko, 2010).

2. Risk management

Risk management is considered as one of the measures that banks take actively and seriously, in parallel with their daily activities. The head office of financial institutions continuously leads and supervises activities that are the source of this financial risk to avoid any problems that may affect their role (Eloitri, 2017)

3. Customer behavior

According to Pride and Farrell (2003), customer behavior is "the process of decisions and actions of people involved in the purchase and use of products or services." Whereas, according to Solomon et al. (2006), "Consumer behavior is the study of the processes involved when individuals or groups choose, buy, use, or dispose of products, services, ideas, or experiences to satisfy needs and desires." (Fejza et al., 2018)

4. Commercial banks

(Abdelkhaleq, 2010) defined commercial banks as the banks that accept deposits paid on demand or for maturities. It carries out internal and external financing operations and its service in a way that achieves the objectives of the development plan, supports the national economy, and embarks on savings and financial investment development processes at home and abroad, including contributing to the establishment of projects, and the banking, commercial and financial operations that are required, in accordance with the conditions set by the Central Bank. While it has been defined by (Albakri et al, 2009) as Business establishments that mainly aim to achieve profit in addition to contributing to the development of the national economy, and the activity of commercial banks is related to the circulation of money in its monetary form, as these banks collect the savings of individuals, establishments and bodies in the form of deposits and invest these deposits in lending to others and other investments that can yield interest on the top The investor's money with the bank, in addition to that, it provides services to clients in return for interest. It also has been defined by (Samhan et al, 2011) as intermediary financial institutions that accumulate savings of individuals and economic units that achieve a surplus and use them to lend to individuals and projects with deficits

5. The Modeling of Deposits

The modeling of deposits and non-maturing liabilities is a critical task for managing liquidity in a financial institution. It has become more important after the liquidity crisis that affected the money market in 2008/2009. ALM departments in banks are usually involved in managing liquidity risk and interest rate, face the task of forecasting the volume of deposits, in order to design and implement the consequent liquidity strategies. Moreover, deposit accounts represent the main source of financing for the bank, especially those institutions that

focus on the retail trade, and contribute significantly to the financing available in each period of the lending activity (Castagna & Manenti, 2013).

6. Related Studies

On this section, this paper attempts to present some studies that addressed the issues of Risk management of liquidity or/and customers behavior issues in commercial banks. For instance, (Regragui and Merioui, 2015) proposed a modeling of the sight deposits of a Moroccan commercial bank customers. They have worked on data from a balance sheet in order to determine the stable part of these deposits, as a function of the time that the bank could use to grant loans while minimizing the risk of liquidity and transformation. They concluded that the filing companies, from these results, have no visible financial behavior with regard to their sight deposits. Another study conducted by (Mehdi & Abderrassoul, 2014) analyzed the liquidity behavior of the Moroccan bank during the period (2001-2012). The authors aimed to identify the determinants of liquidity of the Moroccan bank. First, they assessed the liquidity status of Moroccan banks through different liquidity ratios to determine the effects of the financial crisis on the banks' liquidity. Then they highlighted the effect of the volume of the banks on the liquidity of the banks. Finally, they defined the determinants of the liquidity of the Moroccan bank using the regression data panel. The results showed that liquidity in Moroccan banks, is mainly determined by return on assets, volume of banks, external funding to total liabilities, share of own bank's capital of the bank's total assets, financial crisis and other determinants. However, the return on equity and equity to total assets and the unemployment rate have no effect on the liquidity of the Moroccan bank.

In the article conducted by (Castagna & Manenti, 2013), the authors presented a review of the most important literature and market practice techniques for modeling non-maturing deposit accounts. They described the bond portfolio replication approach and then moved to the category of stochastic factor models, showing how they are able to provide more effective interest rate and liquidity risk management tools for these balance sheet elements. Moreover, (Jaksybekova et al., 2018) through their paper considered innovation tools to assess and manage liquidity risk for second-tier banks. They studied the key concepts of the liquidity risk assessment presented by foreign and local scholars and the main factors for bank liquidity risk have been identified. They also worked on a factor model for assessing liquidity risk as they used the variable asset and liability structure of the second tier bank researched in Kazakhstan. They identified tools for assessing liquidity risk to implement a liquidity risk model.

Furthermore, (Mubarak, 2020) aimed on his study to examine the effectiveness of risk management practices that are represented in liquidity risks and their impact on the financial performance of Islamic banks. Liquidity risk is measured through the ratio of loan to deposit and cash to total assets. The measurement representations of financial performance were return on assets and return on equity. The data was part of 2013-2017 taken from the financial reports of Islamic banks. Regression analysis was used to extract the results. The outcomes determined how liquidity risk affects the financial performance of Egyptian Islamic banks.

Moving to Kosovo, As part of their research, (Fejza et al., 2018) studied and analyzed customer behavior in Kosovar commercial banks. Their study was divided into three major parts: The first reviewed various publications, literature and scientific journals in order to understand the role and importance of customer behavior in organizations. The second part, included a survey questionnaire with a sample base of randomly selected 500 individual customers from commercial banks in Kosovo to determine the behavior of existing customers in the banking sector, and to analyze the various external and internal factors that influence such behaviors. In the last part, the data obtained from the literature review and questionnaire surveys were used to draw conclusions about the central issues of this research and to make recommendations that may be useful to commercial banks in Kosovo. While (Eloitri, 2017) research paper focused on the banking sector and bank liquidity in the Moroccan interbank. The volatility of liquidity was the result of an increase in the money supply within the interbank market before 2007. Immediately after that year, and after the mortgage crises, the interbank market reached the point of illiquidity, and banks began to request refunds from the central bank. This demand was increasing every week, and to this day, Moroccan banks have not succeeded in solving this issue, neither by satisfying the lack of liquidity nor through the surplus liquidity in their coffers.

7. Discussion

Modeling of sight deposits using an econometric approach

Data Description

The study we propose to carry out is a modeling of sight deposits for "business" customers of the banks. The data on which we have worked come from the summary "balance sheet" statements of this same bank and which concern the monthly outstanding deposits of "business" customers since their evolution depends on the customer behavior which may be financial, economic or seasonal. Once chosen, the model will make it possible to establish a stability threshold for sight deposits which constitutes the part of these that the bank will have for its various uses and without great risk of becoming payable.

Presentation of Data

For the purposes of modeling, in addition to the series of month-end stocks of the various accounts subject to modeling, there is a need for a series of interest rates and a series of remuneration rates. This study uses, as interest rate variable, the series of market rates of the Treasury bills issued by auction to 52 weeks extracted from the site of BAM. The series taken into account is a series of monthly rates that runs from December 2001 to October 2020. Depending on the needs of each model, the paper extracted part of this series. Its evolution over time is represented by the graph below.

Modelling of demand deposits remunerated

In this section we explain the approach and results for the modeling of demand deposits for a remunerated account: Savings account.

We have data from December 2001 to October 2020. The following graph shows the evolution of outstanding amounts for this account.

Outstandings are trending upwards, a jump in May 2010 corresponding to an overall change of 407.83% between December 2001 and October 2020.

We choose to split the learning base (on which will be carried out the modelling-December 2001-December 2017) and the validation basis (on which will be carried out the backtest-January 2018-November 2020)

1 -Jarrow& Van Deventer model

Jarrow and Van Deventer's model reads as follows: $\log D_k - \log D_{k-1} = \alpha_1 + \alpha_2 t_k + \alpha_3 R_k + \alpha_4 (R_k - R_{k-1})$

Where:

D_k : outstanding demand deposits at time k

R_k : The market rate

t_k : linear trend of time representing macroeconomic variables

The estimate of the current account and check account by the Eviews software gives us the exit:

Dependent Variable : $\log D_k - \log D_{k-1}$					
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.	
C	0.022616	0.043693	0.517599	0.6057	
t_k	-9.85E-05	0.000120	-0.820963	0.4134	
R_k	-0.034897	0.953171	-0.036612	0.9709	
$R_k - R_{k-1}$	0.427491	2.109323	0.202667	0.8398	
R-squared	0.038675				
Adjusted R-squared	0.013813			Mean dependent var	
S.E. of regression	0.016576			S.D. dependent var	
Sum squared resid	0.031874			Akaike info criterion	
Log likelihood	323.7351			Schwarz criterion	
F-statistic	1.555595			Hannan-Quinn write.	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.203977				

The Jarrow and Van Deventer model after parameter estimation is thus written as follows: $\log D_{k+1} - \log D_k = 0,0226 - 9,85 \times 10^{-5} t_k - 0,0366 R_k - 0,4274 (D_{k+1} - D_k)$

At the 5% significance threshold, we can consider that no variable of our model is significant because the P-value of our model (Prob.) is greater than 5%.

2-Estimating the O'brien model

O'brien's model reads as follows: $\log D_k = \alpha_1 + \alpha_2(R_k - i_k) + \alpha_3 t_k + \alpha_4 \log D_{k-1}$

The estimated current account and check account by the Eviews software gives us the following output:

Dependent Variable : $\log D_k - \log D_{k-1}$				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.356612	0.258713	1.378407	0.1707
$(R_k - i_k)$	0.216974	0.485008	0.447363	0.6554
@TREND	0.000132	0.000187	0.702409	0.4838
$\log D_{k-1}$	0.968349	0.024442	39.61788	0.0000
R-squared	0.996080		Mean dependent var	11.64622
Adjusted R-squared	0.995979		S.D. dependent var	0.258484
S.E. of regression	0.016391		Akaike info criterion	-5.351408
Sum squared resid	0.031165		Schwarz criterion	-5.258492
Log likelihood	325.0845		Hannan-Quinn write.	-5.313674
F-statistic	9826.023		Durbin-Watson stat	2.193569
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

The O'Brien model after the parameter estimation will therefore be written: $\log D_k = 0,3566 + 0,2169(R_k - i_k) + 0,000132t_k + 0,9683\log D_{k-1}$

If we consider the significance threshold of 5%, we can say that time has a significant influence on the balance of the cheque and current account. On the other hand, the delayed value of the stock of the current account and cheque account significantly influences the stock of that account, more precisely when the delayed value of the current account and cheque account increases by one percent, its present value would increase all other things equal by 0.96%. On the other hand, at this same threshold of significance (5%), we could consider the stock of the current account and check account is inelastic at the interest rate.

Choice of model

The O'Brien Model is the model to be retained because of its great co-determination and the fact that it minimizes the information criteria.

Validation of the model

We will test homoscedasticity using the ARCH test to detect a possible ARCH effect in our residues. But first let's start with the correlogram of residue squared.

Autocorrelation	Partial Correlation	AC	PAC	Q-Stat	Prob	
		1	-0.000	-0.000	6.E-06	0.998
		2	-0.006	-0.006	0.0041	0.998
		3	-0.007	-0.007	0.0098	1.000
		4	-0.007	-0.007	0.0165	1.000
		5	-0.008	-0.008	0.0245	1.000
		6	-0.009	-0.009	0.0349	1.000
		7	-0.005	-0.005	0.0376	1.000
		8	-0.007	-0.007	0.0439	1.000
		9	-0.009	-0.009	0.0537	1.000
		10	-0.009	-0.009	0.0644	1.000
		11	-0.008	-0.009	0.0739	1.000
		12	-0.006	-0.007	0.0789	1.000
		13	-0.004	-0.005	0.0813	1.000
		14	-0.008	-0.008	0.0898	1.000
		15	-0.009	-0.009	0.1005	1.000
		16	-0.008	-0.008	0.1088	1.000
		17	-0.009	-0.010	0.1215	1.000
		18	-0.009	-0.010	0.1340	1.000
		19	-0.002	-0.003	0.1345	1.000
		20	-0.002	-0.003	0.1349	1.000

The correlation of the residuals to the square suggests that there is no link between the residuals squares. We will still do the ARCH test with a delay.

ARCH Heteroscedasticity Test

Heteroskedasticity Test: ARCH

F-statistic	5.80E-06	Prob. F(1,117)	0.9981
Obs*R-squared	5.90E-06	Prob. Chi-Square(1)	0.9981

The value of our chi-square probability (1) corresponding to the obs*R-squared statistic is 0.9769<5% so the errors are homoscedastic.

Error autocorrelation test (Breusch-Godfrey)

Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test

F-statistic	0.295066	Prob. F(2,114)	0.7450
Obs*R-squared	0.617992	Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0.7342

The p-value of our test is greater than 5%, which results in the rejection of the null hypothesis of autocorrelation of errors. So the errors are not auto-correlated.

Sight deposit Flow from a Paid Account

The parameters of the previously adjusted model allow us to calculate the speed

Adjustment $\lambda = 3.34\%$, .

Using the flow dynamics equation: $D_t = D^* + (D_0 - D^*) \exp(-\lambda t)$ initial stock is cleared D_0

The coefficient of variation calculated on the data series is 47.13%. This means

47.13% of current account liability deposits are volatile and flow very slowly. The stable portion, which accounts for 56% of the bank's deposits, will be disposed of on a straight-line basis over an H horizon.

Date month	in	Outstanding	Elapsed percentage
0		168962.65	1.84
1		165852.41	1.78
2		162844.33	1.72
3		159935.07	4.83
6		151768.21	8.33
12		137696.23	3.58
15		131649.70	2.19
17		127942.47	3.03
20		122825.90	0.94
21		121231.18	0.91
22		119688.84	0.88
23		118197.16	2.48
26		114009.75	23.52
496		74277.91	0.00
499		74277.91	0.00
500		74277.91	0.00
505		74277.91	0.00
510		74277.91	0.00
520		74277.91	0.00
530		74277.91	0.00
540		74277.91	-

56.04 Stable portion

43.96 Unstable part

Modeling and disposal of sight deposits from an unpaid account

Estimation of the Selvaggio model

The Selvaggio model is written as follows: $\log D_k = \alpha_1 + \alpha_2 t_k + \alpha_3 \log D_{k-1} + \alpha_4 \text{Log} R_k$

The estimated current account and check account by the Eviews software gives us the following output:

Dependent Variable : $\log D_k$				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
α_1	1.252668	0.564286	2.219916	0.0284
t_k	0.000489	0.000247	1.984924	0.0495
$\log D_{k-1}$	0.895344	0.045469	19.69114	0.0000
$\text{Log} R_k$	-0.008884	0.010717	-0.828917	0.4089
R-squared	0.998479		Mean dependent var	11.64622
Adjusted R-squared	0.998439		S.D. dependent var	0.258484
S.E. of regression	0.006919		Akaike info criterion	-5.351408
Sum squared resid	0.005554		Schwarz criterion	-5.258492
Log likelihood	428.5747		Hannan-Quinn write.	-5.313674
F-statistic	25374.96		Durbin-Watson stat	2.193569
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

The Selvaggio model after the parameter estimation will therefore be written: $\log D_k = 1,2526 + 0,00048t_k + 0,8953\log D_{k-1} - 0,0088\text{Log} R_k$

If we consider the significance threshold of 5%, we can say that time has a significant influence on the balance of the cheque and current account. The same shall apply to the delayed value of the stock of the current account and cheque account significantly influences the stock of that account, more precisely when the delayed value of the current account and cheque account increases by one percent, its present value would increase all other things equal by 89%. On the other hand, at this same threshold of significance (5%), the interest rate could be considered as having no effect on the stock of the cheque and current account and the increase in the maché interest rate would reduce the stock of the cheque and current account.

Dupré Model

The Dupré model is written as follows: $\log D_k - \log D_{k-1} = \alpha_1 + \alpha_2 R_k$

The estimated current account and check account by the Eviews software gives us the following output:

Dependent Variable : $\log D_k - \log D_{k-1}$				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.008460	0.003074	2.752555	0.0064
R_k	-0.039793	0.108417	-0.367041	0.7139
R-squared	0.000598		Mean dependent var	0.007350
Adjusted R-squared	-0.003843		S.D. dependent var	0.008279
S.E. of regression	0.008294		Akaike info criterion	-6.737679

Sum squared resid	0.015480	Schwarz criterion	-6.707503
Log likelihood	766.7266	Hannan-Quinn write.	-6.725503
F-statistic	0.134719	Durbin-Watson stat	2.188408
Prob(F-statistic)	0.713933		

The Dupré model is therefore written: $\log D_k - \log D_{k-1} = 0,0084 - 0,0397R_k$

At the 5% significance threshold, we can consider that no variable of our model is significant because the P-value of our model (Prob.) is greater than 5%.

Estimation of OTS

The OTS model is therefore written as follows: $D_k = \alpha D_{k-1}$

The estimated current account and check account by the Eviews software gives us the following output:

		Dependent Variable : D_k		
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D_{k-1}	1.004981	0.000636	1581.142	0.0000
R-squared	0.998391		Mean dependent var	406805.4
Adjusted R-squared	0.998391		S.D. dependent var	71316.26
S.E. of regression	2860.983		Akaike info criterion	18.76402
Sum squared resid	9.74E+08		Schwarz criterion	18.78725
Log likelihood	-1124.841		Hannan-Quinn write.	18.77345
F-statistic	2.835581		Durbin-Watson stat	406805.4
Prob(F-statistic)	0.998391			

The OTS model is therefore written: $D_k = 1,0049D_{k-1}$

At the 5% significance threshold, we can consider the delayed value of the outstanding is significant because the P-value (Prob.) is less than 5%.

Choice of model

The Selvagio Model is the model to be retained because of its great co-determination and the fact that it minimizes most of the information criteria.

Validation of the model

Jarque-Bera Residual Normality Test

The p-value of our test is greater than 5% so our residuals are normally distributed.

We will then test the homoskedasticity using the ARCH test to detect a possible ARCH effect in our residues. But first let's start with the correlogram of residue squared.

Autocorrelation	Partial Correlation	AC	PAC	Q-Stat	Prob	
		1	0.230	0.230	6.5339	0.011
		2	0.066	0.014	7.0800	0.029
		3	-0.010	-0.030	7.0932	0.069
		4	0.023	0.033	7.1614	0.128
		5	0.019	0.010	7.2090	0.206
		6	0.010	0.000	7.2212	0.301
		7	-0.175	-0.187	11.186	0.131
		8	-0.115	-0.038	12.923	0.115
		9	-0.079	-0.032	13.757	0.131
		10	-0.004	0.018	13.759	0.184
		11	-0.114	-0.121	15.519	0.160
		12	-0.037	0.019	15.709	0.205
		13	-0.084	-0.063	16.668	0.215
		14	0.065	0.076	17.257	0.243
		15	0.088	0.046	18.328	0.246
		16	-0.060	-0.132	18.839	0.277
		17	0.000	0.054	18.839	0.338
		18	0.112	0.088	20.651	0.297
		19	-0.061	-0.147	21.192	0.326
		20	-0.029	-0.039	21.313	0.379

The square residue correlogram allows us to include a single delay in our ARCH test

ARCH Residual Test

Heteroskedasticity Test: ARCH

F-statistic	6.608725	Prob. F(1,117)	0.0114
Obs*R-squared	6.362320	Prob. Chi-Square(1)	0.0117

Our ARCH test confirms the heteroscedasticity of our errors because the probability corresponding to our obs*R-squared statistic is $0.0114 < 5\%$. So we have to estimate our model with ARCH (1) effect to correct heteroscedasticity.

The estimation results of our ARCH error model are therefore:

Variable	Dependent Variable : $\log D_{k-1}$		t-Statistic	Prob.
α_1	Coefficient	Std. Error	1.655688	0.0978
t_k	0.734128	0.443397	1.421459	0.1552
$\log D_{k-1}$	0.000272	0.000191	26.24785	0.0000
$\log R_k$	0.937483	0.035717	-1.010426	0.3123
	-0.010635	0.010525		
	Variance equation			
C	3.38E-05	5.78E-06	5.840059	0.0000
RESID(-1) 2	0.266871	0.176713	1.510194	0.1310
R-squared	0.998467		Mean dependent var	12.90090
Adjusted R-squared	0.998427		S.D. dependent var	0.175138
S.E. of regression	0.006946		Akaike info criterion	-7.092265
Sum squared resid	0.005596		Schwarz criterion	-6.952891
Log likelihood	431.5359		Hannan-Quinn write.	-7.035665
F-statistic	2.778366		Durbin-Watson stat	12.90090
Prob(F-statistic)	0.998467			

The results are almost identical for the post-estimation model coefficients: $\log D_k = 0,7341 - 0,00027t_k + 0,9374\log D_{k-1} - 0,0106\log R_k$

8. Conclusion

It is concluded that the outstanding corporate sight deposits with the commercial bank is significantly insensitive to interest rates. The proposed assumption made about rationality in the management of companies' assets, and therefore, their sight deposits with the bank among others, would be rejected according to the results

of the estimations. However, it is remained very cautious with regard to these interpretations since the goodness of fit of the model perceived through the R^2 . It is recommended for further studies on the subject should be carried out to justify this aspect.

The typology of “business” customers at the commercial bank, some companies might not have an opportunistic view of their money. The current accounts they have only present a means of sight payment for their day-to-day transactions. To see more clearly, a study could be made on the basis of more detailed data on the companies. A classification of this could identify those that would be effectively sensitive to investment opportunities, whether in term accounts, bonds, stock market investments, etc.

The model which does not take into account the interactions between current accounts (unpaid) and term accounts; it may indeed turn out that the volume of sight deposits could have been greater if companies did not make term investments. This assumption, although very important, nevertheless remains to be verified and some studies presented more detailed studies which would be based on a vision of all banking establishments and all the products they offer.

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